

Establishment of the OH-FINE OFC

Establishing the foundations for a dynamic and interactive Organic Farming Learning Community

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PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page))	X
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Table of content

1. Introduction5

1.1 Overall objectives of the OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community in the OH-FINE project5

1.2 Scope of the OH-FINE OFC6

1.3 Aim of the report6

2. Creation of the Organic Farming Community7

2.1 Creation of 5 Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hub in Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, and Spain8

2.2 Creation of the online Organic Farming Community environment9

2.3 Prioritization of needs and thematic focus11

2.4 European dynamic Stakeholder and knowledge entities database12

3. Organisation of the first OH-FINE forum14

4. Monitoring of the OFC15

5. Awareness raising actions17

6. Next steps17

7. Annexes18

Annex 1: **19**..... 19

Annex 2: OFC Monitoring plan of RKH activities**24**

Annex 3: **33**actions..... 33

Executive Summary

Deliverable 3.2 outlines the establishment of the OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community (OFC), a central component of the OH-FINE project designed to act as the operational backbone of OH-FINE connecting all pillars – knowledge mapping, knowledge exchange, co-creation, training, DSS development and dissemination- into a coherent system, to accelerate the adoption of organic farming practices across Europe.

The OFC provides a permanent, pan-European ecosystem where farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers, and value-chain actors collaborate through both digital and physical channels. Its structure enables the translation of research and multi-actor insights into accessible, practice-oriented knowledge aligned with on-farm needs.

At the heart of the OFC are **five Regional Knowledge Hubs (RKHs)** established in Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, and Spain. These hubs function as decentralised platforms for farmer engagement, training, field trials, networking, and co-creation activities adapted to regional climatic, agronomic, and socio-economic conditions. Each hub is developed using a structured stakeholder mapping methodology and benefits from clear guidelines for workshop organisation, engagement processes, and activity planning. Dedicated RKH spaces have been integrated into the OH-FINE digital platform to ensure seamless alignment between physical and digital knowledge exchange.

The **OFC's digital environment** has been designed as an integrated architecture connecting the RKHs, Decision Support System (DSS), and community services. Work included defining governance, content workflows, user experience prototypes, and digital communication channels.

The **OFC's thematic focus** will be grounded in a comprehensive needs assessment from WP2 complemented with new emerging needs during the activities, highlighting farmers' priorities related to EU policy, organic compliance, soil and pest management, labour-saving technologies, market access, and animal health. A **dynamic European stakeholder database** will be developed to support multi-actor involvement.

Additionally, progress includes the successful organisation of the first **OH-FINE Forum**, the creation of a detailed OFC monitoring framework, and the preparation of tailored awareness-raising guidelines. Next steps concentrate on platform operationalisation, content integration, outreach, and continuous monitoring to ensure long-term impact and community growth.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Overall objectives of the OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community in the OH-FINE project

The Organic Farming Learning Community (OFC) is a central instrument within the OH-FINE project to achieve the project's overarching goal: empowering European farmers and smallholders through the creation, enhancement and transfer of competitive, efficient, and practice-oriented organic farming knowledge and expertise.

The OFC contributes to the OH-FINE's strategic objectives, by:

- Providing a permanent, pan-European ecosystem for knowledge exchange among farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers, and value-chain actors involved in organic farming.
- Collecting, disseminating, and translating research and multi-actor knowledge into easily accessible, actionable, practice-oriented knowledge, supporting farmers in both conversion and post-conversion phases.
- Strengthening AKIS structures by connecting regional and (European) organic farming communities, facilitating cross-fertilization, and reducing fragmentation in knowledge flows.
- Accelerating the adoption of innovative organic practices by bridging the “advice-to-action” gap identified across partner countries.

Through these objectives, the OFC acts as the operational backbone of OH-FINE, connecting all pillars—knowledge mapping, co-creation, training, DSS development, and dissemination—into a coherent system.

The OFC will be developed and operationalized by:

- creation of 5 Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hub in Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, and Spain
- implementing a multi-agent online learning system, validated in five case study regions across Europe.
- developing a digital platform and Decision Support System (DSS) that make the OFC interactive, scalable, and widely accessible.
- organizing stakeholder events and participatory activities to promote engagement and knowledge exchange.

Within WP3, the OFC is developed as a structured, collaborative space where farmers, experts, and other stakeholders interact. Its architecture defines communication channels, information flows, and collaboration mechanisms, ensuring that project findings are shared, validated, and further developed.

This structure establishes a direct link between the OFC in WP3, the WP4 OH-FINE Platform and DSS and other OH-FINE activities in other work packages (WP's), enabling seamless integration across work packages and reinforcing the project's overall impact.

1.2 Scope of the OH-FINE OFC

The OFC will integrating digital and physical channels to create a permanent community of practice in organic farming. Its scope includes:

- **Geographical coverage and diversity:** five regional contexts (Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, Spain), complemented by insights from Austria, Belgium, and Switzerland and the wider EU region where relevant.
- **Thematic coverage and priorities:** the project focuses on cereals, oilseeds, protein crops, and livestock systems. The OFC spans the full spectrum of knowledge needs in organic farming—from technical production methods to socio-economic, environmental, and digital dimensions. It is deliberately guided by the **specific needs and priorities of farmers in the case study countries**, ensuring that all OFC activities remain relevant, actionable, and grounded in real practice.
- **Stakeholder range:** The OFC is designed as a truly **multi-actor community**, involving a broad range of stakeholders essential to knowledge flow, innovation, and decision-making within organic farming including producers (conventional, in-conversion, organic), advisors, researchers, NGOs, policymakers, agri-food companies, consumers, and technology developers.
- **Knowledge formats:** The OFC integrates a wide variety of learning formats to accommodate different user needs and contexts, including field trials, workshops, cross-visits, technical documents, practice abstracts, training activities, videos, DSS-integrated guidance, forums, and a multilingual digital knowledge repository.

1.3 Aim of the report

The aim of this report is to present the initial set-up and structural foundations of the Organic Farming Learning Community (OFC) within the OH-FINE project. It provides an overview of the initial design work, stakeholder mapping, and community architecture that together provide the basis for a functional European knowledge-exchange network.

The report describes the first phase of the OFC development, during which the essential components — governance, stakeholder typology, Regional Knowledge Hubs creation, preliminary digital structures, and monitoring plan—have been established. The purpose is to ensure that the community is coherently designed, inclusive, and aligned with the needs of the case-study farmers, thereby preparing the ground for a more dynamic, interactive, and participatory stakeholder engagement process in the next phase of the project.

2. Creation of the Organic Farming Community

The Organic Farming Learning Community (OFC) established in WP3 is structured around interconnected components that collectively support knowledge exchange, stakeholder engagement, and innovation in organic agriculture in close collaboration with other WPs in the project:

- **Regional Knowledge Hubs (RKHs)** Five regional hubs (Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, and Spain) function as localized platforms for knowledge transfer. They facilitate practical activities such as training, workshops, field trials, and networking, tailored to regional farming conditions.
- **Stakeholder Network and Database** A dynamic European-wide database identifying relevant stakeholders and knowledge entities. It ensures broad participation and provides the foundation for collaboration and information sharing within the OFC.
- **Stakeholder Engagement and Participatory Processes** Structured engagement activities, including workshops, forums, demonstration and interactive sessions, designed to foster collaboration, integrate diverse perspectives, and co-create solutions to challenges in organic farming.
- **Monitoring and Evaluation Framework** A system of tools and procedures to assess participation, effectiveness, and impact of OFC activities, allowing continuous improvement and identification of best practices.
- **Awareness-Raising and Communication Actions** Clearly defined actions aimed at increasing awareness of organic farming benefits, addressing adoption barriers, and promoting stakeholder involvement at regional and European levels.

The OH-FINE project in a nutshell (coordination, support measures, and methodology) with the Organic Farming Learning pan-European Community (OFC) at the centre of the project activities. (Infographic: CISC)

2.1 Creation of 5 Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hub in Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, and Spain

The **Regional Knowledge Hubs (RKH)** are a central component of the OFC, acting as key nodes for identifying needs and the exchange and application of context-specific organic farming knowledge. The establishment of five Regional Organic Farming Knowledge Hubs (RKHs) across Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria, and Spain is essential to address the diverse agronomic, climatic, and socio-economic conditions that characterize European agriculture. A single, uniform approach to knowledge transfer is insufficient; instead, regionally adapted hubs ensure that organic farming solutions are relevant, practical, and impactful.

Therefore, in each case study region, the cases study producers will be supported by a Regional Knowledge Hub (RKH). Each hub serves as a focal point for gathering, sharing, and applying organic farming knowledge and practices tailored to the regional characteristics and needs. This is achieved by combining regional expert insights with collaborations from farming associations and research entities. Activities include establishing connections with local stakeholders and engaging in workshops, training sessions, field trials, and networking events.

By tailoring knowledge exchange to regional needs, the RKHs will significantly enhance the effectiveness of advisory services and increase the adoption of organic farming practices. This localized approach ensures meaningful engagement, contributing to the target of five active hubs with together at least 100 participants involved in case studies, while improving sustainability outcomes across diverse European farming systems.

To assist the RKH managers, a stakeholder mapping and analysis guideline was developed to support the establishment of the RKHs in the respective countries (see Annex 1). This guideline enables them to assess local networks and identify individuals and organizations interested in participating in the hubs. A workshop guideline was prepared, including a stakeholder mapping methodology linking relevant actors to specific needs identified for each case study region through a WP2 survey. For each prioritized need, case study farmers and the RKH coordinator identify who should be contacted, as well as how, why, and when engagement should take place. This process is supported by the experience and knowledge of the Regional Knowledge Hub managers and their national partners, as well as by the results and findings related to the overall organic AKIS structure in the respective regions ([Deliverable 2.3 – Section 5](#), [Deliverables 2.4 and 2.5](#)).

In each of the 5 RKH partner country, this analysis has been conducted, and Regional Knowledge Hub managers have begun personally contacting several of the identified stakeholders to explain the project and how the hubs operate. RKH participants are expected to develop, together with the RKH manager, a schedule of activities and meet regularly to monitor the hub's performance.

These activities will be aligned with the OH-FINE activities carried out in other work packages (WP5, WP6, WP7), such as training courses and field demonstrations. These will form the core of the activities in the hubs and will be included in the overall activity calendar.

Within this context, and to provide digital support for the knowledge hubs, a dedicated space for each RKH has been established on the OH-FINE platform (in WP4). The digital services and functionalities available to stakeholders have been defined, along with interaction points among RKH managers. Bilateral meetings have been conducted between Betania, responsible for WP4, and the managers of each RKH have resulted in a standardized working methodology ensuring a continuous flow of information. Furthermore, IT tests regarding design and functionality are currently ongoing.

2.2 Creation of the online Organic Farming Community environment

As one of the first steps in the development of the OFC environment, the OFC architecture was constructed as the structural, methodological, and relational foundation of the platform within WP4. This platform will be the central digital infrastructure of the OH-FINE OFC knowledge and information exchange and online interactions. Further detail on the development of the platform is provided in [Deliverable 4.1. OH-FINE Platform architecture](#).

The OH-FINE Community (OFC) framework establishes a comprehensive structure for roles, governance, workflows, and service delivery. It defines structured services such as training, resources, and co-creation spaces, while also specifying the integration of Regional Knowledge Hubs (RKH) and aligning community architecture with platform functionalities.

The groundwork has included:

Stakeholder Mapping and Mobilisation: Building on WP2 results, key stakeholders—including farmers—were analysed in terms of needs, interests, and influence. This informed the initial design of the OFC architecture, services, and functionalities.

Interface and User Experience Design: A preliminary visual prototype of the OFC platform was developed and presented to the project partners. Feedback from partners guided improvements in both visual identity and functional aspects.

Community Architecture Development: Once the architecture was defined, each section of its structure was further elaborated. In this initial phase, the lines of work were outlined so that each partner, depending on their expertise and field of action, assumes specific responsibilities to provide coverage and content for each part of the OH FINE Community, thus contributing to its progressive development.

These activities have entailed, for each area of the Community:

- **Establishment of the organizational and governance structure** of each OH FINE community service. Roles, responsibilities, and coordination mechanisms among partners have been established.
- **Identification of the content and services** to be made available to farmers and key stakeholders. Key resources, digital tools, learning spaces, exchange, and collaboration environments, among others, have been identified.
- **Specification of the criteria and functionalities** to be incorporated into the DSS and Compass ICT tools, which will provide information and support community members in their transition to organic farming.
- **Design of digital channels to inform and connect community members.** Online registration and subscription channels have been created. A working methodology has been designed to promote the OH FINE community from the physical and/or local level to its digital level.

This process includes:

- **The strategic design of the knowledge architecture:** This is, the structure and navigation of the RKH within the platform have been defined, along with the connectors to other modules (DSS, resources, etc.).
- **A detailed design and technological integration** (functional and technical specifications): Functional requirements have been determined, and interoperability with other platform systems has been defined. In addition, IT tests of design and functionality have been carried out.

- **Content development to feed each RKH:** tools have been developed for partners to collect and present this content; and protocols, processes, and update timelines have been designed. A commitment to the proposed work plan of the regional knowledge hub manager is essential to success of the OH-FINE OFC as an essential component.

The digital learning platform works in close collaboration with other OH-FINE work packages such as WP3.3 (forum with workshops and interactive learning and knowledge sharing sessions), WP5 and WP6 (on-ground training sessions, technical workshops, video's and technical documents, collaboration with relevant projects, and cross-visits), WP7 (video's and technical documents), WP9 (policy briefs), WP 10, WP11 and WP12 (practice abstracts, scientific publications, collaboration with other projects) to feed the platform with validated content.

2.3 Prioritization of needs and thematic focus

The design and implementation of OFC activities will be strongly informed by the needs assessment conducted in WP2 among farmers involved in the five OH-FINE partner countries with case study groups. An analysis of needs and challenges was carried out (see *Deliverable 2.5: Defining Specific Knowledge Needs*), yielding several key findings:

Relevant findings are:

- At a general level, farmers prioritise knowledge related to **EU policy and subsidies, environmental sustainability, market information, soil and pest management, and organic compliance**. These needs reflect the dual challenge of ensuring regulatory alignment while maintaining economic viability and environmental performance. Organic compliance emerges as a cross-cutting concern, perceived as complex, dynamic, and time-intensive, especially by farmers in the conversion phase.
- From a technological perspective, farmers express **strong interest in practical solutions**, notably in soil and pest management, labour-saving tools, short supply chains, and animal health. This indicates a clear demand for applied innovation-oriented knowledge that can improve farm efficiency and resilience.

The analysis also reveals important differences across farmer profiles.

- **In-conversion farmers (and post conversion farmers)** demonstrate the highest demand for support related to organic compliance and EU policies, underlining the complexity and intensity of the transition phase. They also show a strong interest in labour-saving technologies and targeted training on soil health, manure, and compost management, as well as animal breeding, nutrition, and integrated crop-livestock systems.
- **Conventional farmers** express concerns about the profitability of adopting organic practices and highlight the need for peer-to-peer learning opportunities with farmers already implementing innovative organic approaches.

The survey also provides important insights into communication and engagement strategies. Farmers predominantly **rely on traditional and practice-oriented channels, such as legacy media (TV, radio, newspapers), farming press, farm walks, open days, and demonstration trials**. This preference is particularly pronounced in countries such as Poland and Spain, where digital tool uptake remains comparatively low. Furthermore, farmers clearly favour experiential and peer-based learning formats, with on-farm demonstrations, live training sessions, and visits to innovative farms identified as the most effective approaches.

In terms of thematic priorities for training and innovation, key topics include pasture management, animal feeding, organic livestock fattening, direct sales, organic weed control, crop rotation, and soil improvement. These areas will therefore constitute core thematic pillars of OFC activities.

Overall, these findings underline the importance of designing OFC activities that are practice-oriented, farmer-centred, and tailored to distinct stages of the organic transition. A balanced approach combining technical guidance, regulatory support, and peer-to-peer exchange—delivered through both physical and digital channels—will be essential to effectively address farmers' needs and ensure strong engagement within the OFC community.

2.4 European dynamic Stakeholder and knowledge entities database

Establishing a dynamic and comprehensive database of stakeholders and knowledge entities is a central pillar for the successful development and functioning of the OFC. Addressing the evolving challenges and knowledge needs of organic farming requires the involvement of a diverse range of actors and expertise, reflecting the complexity of agricultural systems and value chains. Given this diversity—and the already wide range of stakeholders engaged across different WP's—a continuously evolving stakeholder mapping process is essential to support effective collaboration, knowledge exchange, and innovation.

The database provides an overview of key actors contributing to the implementation of project tasks across the WPs. It facilitates the identification, engagement, and mobilisation of stakeholders and knowledge holders, thereby supporting the development of a European-wide network dedicated to advancing organic agriculture. This approach fosters a multi-actor environment that integrates diverse perspectives, enhances knowledge flows, promotes co-creation, and supports informed decision-making.

To structure this process, a 15-category stakeholder typology has been established, ensuring balanced and inclusive representation of the organic farming ecosystem. The categories include:

- Conventional farmers and livestock breeders
- Farmers and livestock breeders converting to organic farming

- Organic farmers and livestock breeders
- Advisors and consultants
- Policy makers, public administration, and regulatory bodies
- Input suppliers
- Processors
- Distributors
- Retailers
- Certification bodies
- Educational communities
- Scientific communities
- Consumers and citizens
- Technology developers and innovators
- Other relevant actors

The database builds existing resources, including regional Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) analyses conducted under WP2, as well as Regional Knowledge Hub (RKH) network analyses and participant lists from project activities. At the same time, it remains open and adaptive, continuously expanding to incorporate new stakeholders in response to emerging knowledge needs and project challenges.

Operationally, the database is maintained through a shared Excel file compiling detailed information on stakeholders who have participated in OH-FINE activities or have consented to receive project-related information. In addition to standard contact details, it includes fields such as gender, age, and country of origin, as well as consent-related information, ensuring full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). All project partners are responsible for regularly updating stakeholder information, following each OFC activity and throughout the development of RKH networks and case study group activities.

At the current stage of the project, this stakeholder database is considered an **internal operational tool**, intended solely for use within the OH-FINE consortium. The current consent obtained from stakeholders is strictly limited to internal project purposes and does not permit the sharing of personal data beyond the partnership. This approach reflects the stringent requirements of GDPR about personal data processing and ensures that stakeholder information is handled in a secure and responsible manner.

Stakeholders identified through this process and have given their consent are invited to become active members of the OFC and participate in its activities. The database also supports the selection of experts aligned with specific project needs, ensuring that relevant knowledge and expertise are mobilised effectively.

In addition, stakeholders visiting different sections of the online OH-FINE platform will be invited to join the community by completing an online registration form, subject to clearly defined consent conditions. This coordinated approach ensures that the database remains current and reflective of the evolving stakeholder landscape.

Overall, this dynamic European stakeholder database will serve as a key internal operational tool for the OH-FINE project. By supporting a broad and active multi-actor community, it will enable systematic engagement, facilitate information sharing, strengthen participation in OFC activities, enhance knowledge exchange, foster innovation, and contribute to the long-term impact and sustainability of the project.

3. Organisation of the first OH-FINE forum

The first OH-FINE Forum, “Cultivating the Future: Organic and Regenerative in Action,” was held on 10 October 2025 in Zamora, Spain, alongside the Ecocultura fair. Organised collaboratively by IRNASA–CSIC, SEAE, and ILVO, it was the inaugural event of three international forums of the OH-FINE project, serving as a milestone for knowledge exchange, stakeholder engagement, and the creation of the OH-FINE Organic Farming Learning Community.

Given the early stage of the project, the forum adopted a broad and forward-looking theme of regenerative organic farming. The programme combined:

- An expert keynote presentation to set the stage for discussions
- A high-level panel debate involving experts and policymakers
- Farmer-led practical case studies showcasing on-the-ground solutions
- Three interactive workshops addressing:
 - Techniques and farm management
 - Challenges facing young people in agriculture
 - Opportunities for collaboration among European projects
- A roundtable discussion exploring market opportunities for regenerative organic products

The workshops generated valuable insights into future OH-FINE activities, highlighting the need for context-specific regenerative solutions, stronger farmer-to-farmer knowledge exchange, improved access to technology, reduced administrative barriers, and targeted support for young entrants into agriculture. Additionally, the session with European project coordinators revealed strong potential for future collaboration, joint dissemination, and data sharing across projects.

With a hybrid format, the forum brought together 261 participants—138 in person and 123 online—representing 30 countries and a diverse range of stakeholders, including farmers, advisors, researchers, educators, NGOs, and policymakers. Translation services and hybrid participation ensured accessibility for both local and international audiences, reinforcing the forum’s inclusive approach.

Overall, the forum successfully met its objectives by strengthening stakeholder engagement, fostering dialogue between research and practice, and laying the

groundwork for project-wide learning processes. Participants' highly positive feedback confirmed that the forum's format and approach could serve as a model for future events. Recommendations for upcoming forums include securing programmes and speakers early, allocating more time for interaction, improving outreach across partner countries, refining digital monitoring tools, and ensuring strong post-forum follow-up.

The first OH-FINE Forum demonstrated that international collaboration, inclusive dialogue, and practical knowledge sharing can effectively support the transition to regenerative organic farming, setting a solid precedent for the next two forums in the series. For more information on the organization of the first forum see [D3.1 First forum report](#) and the OH-FINE website <https://www.oh-fine.eu/international-forums/first-oh-fine-forum>.

4. Monitoring of the OFC

Monitoring the OFC activities ensures that project objectives are met, progress is tracked, and potential issues are detected early. It provides data for informed decision-making, promotes accountability and transparency among partners, and supports effective reporting and continuous improvement throughout the project.

The objectives of monitoring are to:

- Evaluate implementation quality and effectiveness.
- Measure engagement, knowledge transfer, and stakeholder satisfaction.
- Identify opportunities for improvement and adjust processes in real time.
- Ensure outputs contribute to the adoption of organic farming practices.

The OFC will be monitored on multiple levels:

- **Activity Level** – Each OFC activity, whether in-person or virtual, is monitored individually. Monitoring focuses on participation, implementation quality, and immediate outputs to ensure that activities are delivered as planned and meet their objectives.
- **Regional Knowledge Hub (RKH) Level** – RKHs are key nodes in the OFC, collecting, sharing, and applying context-specific knowledge. A dedicated monitoring plan has been developed for each RKH to assess performance, engagement, and outcomes including the physical level of in-person activities and a digital level related to the platform and digital services.
- **OFC Level** – Monitoring at this level provides a general overview of all activities and levels, ensuring alignment with overall project objectives and KPIs.

Monitoring distinguishes between:

- **RKH-specific activities** (physical or virtual), which are more locally focused, such as meetings with producers, advisory services, training courses, and technical demonstrations.
- **Open activities** available to all stakeholders, including forums, cross-visits, workshops, and use of OH-FINE project materials (videos, practice abstracts, OH-FINE platform and website, technical documentation).

As a central component of the OFC, a detailed **monitoring plan of each RKHs** is written, including:

- **On the physical level – in-person activities**
 - Monitoring objective: to evaluate the implementation of advisory activities, training sessions, technical demonstrations, and farmer support.
 - Key indicators: compliance with the schedule, number and profile of beneficiaries, types of services provided, and documentary evidence.
 - Monitoring tools: attendance records, technical activity reports, advisory meeting minutes, photographic evidence, generated materials, satisfaction surveys, and quality questionnaires.
- **On the virtual level – platform and digital resources**
 - Monitoring objective: to evaluate the provision and use of digital resources, technical tools, training content, and online support services.
 - Key indicators: number of resources published, number of registered users, level of access and usage (downloads, views, interactions, session time), response time to digital queries, and quality of the responses provided (relevance, resolution, pertinence, and clarity).

Beside measurement procedures and protocols, the governance system for the coordination and implementation of RKH monitoring have been designed. The detailed document 'OFC Monitoring plan of RKH activities' providing all detail is included in Annex 2. This Monitoring Plan serves as a strategic instrument to oversee the implementation of RKH activities, ensuring transparency, efficiency, and coherence with the overall objectives of the OH FINE project.

Besides activities developed specific for the case study groups and RKH, other **activities are open for all stakeholders**.

- In all activities guidelines developed in the different OH-FINE WPs, instructions are included to monitoring the attendance and evaluate the satisfaction of the activity. For each of these activities key information is gathered related to the number of participants, type of stakeholders, gender, and age group. Additional for each activity, collected by a survey after the activity, at least the level of satisfaction with the activity, percentage of

attendees that improved their knowledge/skills, and topics of interest for future activities are collected.

- General online engagement in the digital platform is monitored through platform analytics, capturing data on participation, content access and use, user interaction, and collaboration patterns. These metrics provide insights into the effectiveness of digital services and tools in supporting knowledge exchange.

5. Awareness raising actions

As part of the establishment of the OH-FINE Organic Farming Community (OFC), clear and focused objectives have been formulated to guide the awareness-raising actions proposed within the OH-FINE project. These objectives are carefully designed to align with the project's overarching goals and to resonate to the needs and expectations of the identified target audiences. This approach ensures that the project's outcomes of the works conducted are effectively communicated, understood, and adopted by the target audiences, thereby maximizing the social, economic, and environmental impact of the project.

All partners will actively contribute to ensuring that the outcomes of the work conducted are truly useful for different national context and that potential social and cultural differences are considered. To guide this process, a table divided by the project's target audience was created. For each of these groups, it outlines specific awareness-raising objectives, along with the messages we want to convey, potential imitations and bottlenecks, how and through which project activities to reach them, and some specific recommendations. This serves as a guide for partners in planning activities, helping them select the most effective approaches for achieving the OH-FINE project's objectives with each target group (producers, advisors, etc) Annex 3 of this report. includes the guideline document.

6. Next steps

Over the next months, the focus will be on consolidating and operationalizing the OFC platform, updating the internal dynamic database, integrating project outputs, and supporting the effective monitoring of Rural Knowledge Hubs (RKHs). Efforts will prioritize maintaining up-to-date, relevant content, promoting the platform among partners and target audiences, and ensuring that monitoring and feedback mechanisms are fully operational. Partners will be supported in becoming familiar with the established guidelines and tools, while outreach to audiences beyond the consortium will enhance visibility, engagement, and knowledge sharing. These actions aim to strengthen the OFC's impact, facilitate collaboration across different national contexts, and contribute to the long-term sustainability of the OH-FINE project.

7. Annexes

DRAFT

Annex 1

Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hubs (RKH)

Introduction

The RKH in the Grant Agreement: objectives and KPIs

Below are all references to RKHs in the Grant Agreement:

T.3.2. Creation of 5 Organic Farming Regional Knowledge Hub in Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria and Spain. (**LT: CSIC; P: TEAG, LAMMC WULS, IPTP**) (M09-M48). In each study region the cases study producers will be supported by an RKH. Each hub serves as a focal point for gathering, sharing, and applying organic farming knowledge and practices tailored to the regional characteristics and needs. It includes establishing connections with local stakeholders, engage in activities such as workshops, training sessions, field trials, and networking events.

Creation and Scalability of Regional Hubs for Organic Farming. Establish at least 5 regional hubs, each offering a full suite of services and document at least 2 cases of these models being adopted in other regions or product categories.

Methodology – Phase 2- Stage 2: 5 Regional Organic Farming Knowledge Hubs (RKH) across various European regions (Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria and Spain), each addressing unique regional farming challenges. These hubs serve as centres for knowledge exchange, where local advisors, local farming associations and extension services play a crucial role in disseminating information and best practices tailored to regional specificities. They engage a diverse group of stakeholders, including **farmers, advisors, researchers, and organization representatives**, fostering farmer-led innovation and collaborative solution development. The RKHs also align with AKIS, identifying and addressing knowledge gaps. They incorporate feedback mechanisms to assess resource effectiveness and offer 500 personalized advisory services for local organic farming challenges. Each hub focuses on local agricultural needs, **combining regional expert insights with collaborations from farming associations and research entities.**

Impact: Establishment of Regional Organic Farming Knowledge Hubs (RKH): These hubs will serve as localized centres for information exchange, tailored to the specific agricultural conditions and needs of various European regions. They will leverage local expertise and foster community engagement. Need Solved: Enhances accessibility to tailored advice and best practices, leading to improved agricultural practices and increased organic farming in diverse regions. **KPI: 5 active regional hubs, with, at least, 100 active participants in case studies.**

1. Creating the RKH: Network analysis

The analysis focuses on the connections you already have, or you might have to create to establish the RKH.

This **short** video (2:51 min) explains how to analyse your networks:

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dS-wl1aC_0E.

At this initial stage, your RKH will probably include:

- The facilitator of your RKH (Generally, it will be you or someone from your institution as responsible for task 3.2 in your country).
- The 20 producers from your country participating in OH-FINE
- The institutions in your country that are OH-FINE partners (both associations and research institutes)

Now it's time to explore which other actors to include in the RKH.

Step 1. List of factors

Using the concepts explained in the video, make a list of key factors (things that might be important for the conversion to organic farming in your region, for example, knowledge gaps, missing services, innovation needs, ...). Explore **the results for your country in the analysis the structure of the overall organic AKIS** of project partner regions produced by TEAGASC in WP2 ([Deliverable 2.3 – section 5](#); [Deliverable 2.4](#) and [Deliverable 2.5](#)). Considering your experience and knowledge and that of your partners in your country, as well as the results and recommendations of the WP2 deliverables (D2.3, D2.4 and D2.5) you can identify these factors.

For example:

- More information about legislation related to conversion to organic farming is needed
- There is no comprehensive public advisory system supporting the transition to organic production or innovation

Step 2. List of links

Make a list of your missing links: links are people who can create connections where you don't yet have it.

Keep in mind that there may be more than one person capable of making those connections. Focus on individuals who can connect others, not only experts.

For the above examples, these would be possible links (fictitious names and entities):

- Juan Pérez, advisor to the Federation of Organic Advisors of OH-FINland (FOAO). He has extensive knowledge of legal issues.

- Macarena Fernández has worked on the development of the new CAP and lives in the area.
- Technical section of the Department of Agriculture of the local government of OH-FINland. We know Deba Gutiérrez, an agricultural engineer in this section. It would be interesting if she could attend the technical workshops and field demonstrations.

Step 3. Complete your list of stakeholders

After making your list, review the RKH concept we have written in the Grant Agreement (first page of this document). Ensure that you have included all the different stakeholders mentioned in the Grant Agreement (**farmers, advisors, researchers, and organisation representatives**). If any are missing, think of specific people you can add to meet this requirement. Think about the ‘why’ they should be included, are important and how they could be involved.

Be sure to include consumption and marketing initiatives.

Step 4. Complete the table

Now that you have a clear idea of what you want the RKH to be like, organise your thoughts and complete the following table:

Factor	Link: Name and institution	Why to include	How to get him/her involved	When to contact	What is their interest? If applicable: What can we offer them?

Following our previous example, the table would be completed as follows:

Factor	Link: Name and institution (fictive names and institutions)	Why to include	How to get him/her involved	When to contact	What is their interest? What can we offer them?
Legislation related to conversion	e.g. Juan Pérez, advisor in FOAO	Extensive knowledge of the subject, good communicator	Teacher on a training course Then add him to the WhatsApp group, if exists, and introduce him to the OFC.	When we organise the training course, February 2026	Courses to enhance his CV Professional connections
Legislation related to conversion	e.g. Macarena Fernández	Get to know the new CAP well. Live in our region and understand the special characteristics of agriculture here.	Teacher on a training course Then add her to the WhatsApp group and introduce her to the OFC	When we organise the training course, February 2026	Courses to enhance his CV Professional connections Obtain feedback from producers, useful for her work
No comprehensive public advisory system	e.g. Deba Gutiérrez, public employee in the agriculture department of the local government	We have collaborated with her on other projects. She is sensitive to organic farming and could help promote initiatives to improve the advice provided by the public administration.	Invite her to project activities (workshops, field demonstrations). Let her get to know the producers and their concerns first-hand.	When we organise the first technical workshop, June 2026.	Training in organic agriculture. Specialising in advisory services.

Step 5. Repeat the analysis periodically

Every year, re-analyse the hub, look for new (or not yet addressed) knowledge needs and other missing factors, and look for links to connect them.

2. Planning the activities

- Once you have a list of factors, indicate which **three factors** you want to start working on first.
- Send your analysis to CSIC (Task leader) and ILVO (WPL). There may be an overlap with other RKH where they can work together. If CSIC detects any kind of synergy, it will let you know so that you can coordinate your efforts.
- You may also share the list with other OH-FINE members in your country in case they wish to contribute and help complete the information.
- Prepare activities aligned with the factors (topics) you have prioritised. Talk to the partners responsible for **WP5 and WP6 activities** in your country. For example, a technical workshop could be organised on the factors identified. Other activities may include policy briefs, meetings with relevant stakeholders, creation of working groups to address a specific issue, etc.
- Make a **timeline** with the planned activities and when they will take place to ensure the correct implementation of the RKH.
- Perform a periodic analysis to ensure that the RKH is functioning correctly in case corrective measures need to be implemented (at the beginning of the RKH each month, then every 6 months)

3. Dissemination of the RKH and its activities

- Develop a communication strategy. Plan **how you will disseminate the initiative** among the stakeholders (through a presentation day, telephone contact, invitation via social media or email, face-to-face meetings, digital newsletters, through another group or intermediary (e.g., cooperative technicians), etc.).
- For example, you could prepare a **short video** presentation of the hub to post on the OFC platform and send to your contacts.
- Remember to comply with the **GDPR** and ask members for their consent before sending them information. If they register via the regional hubs section on the OFC website, they will need to fill in a form accepting the GDPR. If you invite them by other means, you can send them the link to this form directly.

Annex 2

OFC Monitoring plan of RKH activities

Introduction

This Monitoring Plan provides the framework for the systematic monitoring and evaluation of activities carried out by the Regional Knowledge Hubs (RKH) under the OH FINE project, which aims to develop and promote organic agriculture. The Plan is designed to ensure that RKH activities effectively contribute to the project's objectives, enabling the measurement of progress, quality, and outcomes in each region.

Monitoring will facilitate the collection of both quantitative and qualitative data on implemented activities, supporting evidence-based decision-making and ensuring alignment with OH FINE's established objectives. Furthermore, it will provide a basis for identifying opportunities for improvement, adjusting processes in real time, and ensuring that RKH outputs generate a tangible impact on the adoption of organic farming practices and on knowledge transfer to farmers, institutions, and local communities.

This Monitoring Plan serves as a strategic instrument to oversee the implementation of RKH activities, ensuring transparency, efficiency, and coherence with the overall objectives of the OH FINE project.

1. Objectives

- **Monitor the implementation of RKH activities.**
Ensure that all planned actions are executed in accordance with the project timeline and in full compliance with the quality standards established by the OH FINE project.
- **Assess progress and outcomes.**
Systematically collect quantitative and qualitative data on activity execution, outputs, and engagement of local stakeholders.
- **Ensure coherence with project objectives.**
Verify that RKH interventions are fully aligned with the strategic objectives of OH FINE, thereby facilitating the effective transfer of knowledge, best practices, and technology.
- **Support evidence-based decision-making and continuous improvement.**
Provide timely and actionable information to enable strategy adjustment, resource optimization, and enhanced performance of RKH throughout the project lifecycle.
- **Promote accountability, transparency, and reporting.**
Document the implementation of activities and their results to ensure that all stakeholders, at both regional and consortium level, have access to reliable, verifiable, and transparent information

2. Methodology

The monitoring methodology is based on a dual approach, encompassing the systematic oversight of activities carried out by the RKH at:

- **Physical level:** in-person activities such as advisory services, training sessions, technical demonstrations, and farmer support.
- **Virtual level:** provision of digital resources, technical tools, training materials, and online support services.

The monitoring system integrates both levels within a common framework for operational control and periodic reporting.

2.1. Structuring of Monitoring by Operational Level

A. Physical Level – In-Person Activities

Monitoring will focus on:

- Compliance with the scheduled activity calendar.
- Number and profile of beneficiaries reached.
- Type of services delivered (individual advisory, workshops, demonstrations).
- Documentary evidence of activities carried out.

Monitoring tools:

- Attendance records.
- Technical activity reports.
- Advisory session minutes.
- Photographic evidence and generated materials.
- Farmer satisfaction survey regarding advisory services.
- Quality questionnaire for participants in training and demonstration activities.

B. Virtual Level – Platform and Digital Resources

Monitoring will include:

- Number of resources published (guides, technical sheets, videos, tools).
- Number of registered users.
- Level of access and usage of resources (downloads, views, interactions, session duration, etc.).

- Response time to digital inquiries.

Monitoring Tools:

- Analytics from the digital platform.
- Records of inquiries addressed.
- Automated usage reports.
- User interaction tracking.

2.2. Monitoring Indicators

Operational indicators will be defined separately for each level:

Level	Type of Indicator	Example
Physical	Implementation	% of activities completed vs. planned
Physical	Coverage	Number of farmers advised and trained
Virtual	Production	Number of digital resources published
Virtual	Use	Number of accesses/downloads
Ambos	Management	Compliance with deadlines by RKH partners (submission of documents, activity schedule, etc.)

2.3. Collection and Reporting System.

- The RKH will prepare standardized reports **every two months**, integrating results from both levels.
- Data from the virtual environment will be collected using digital analytics tools.
- Central coordination, through Betania, will consolidate the information and verify consistency, progress, and potential deviations.

2.4. Continuous Monitoring and Operational Adjustments.

The designed monitoring plan will enable:

- Detection of imbalances between physical and virtual activities.
- Identification of low participation or limited digital interaction.
- Adjustment of schedules, reinforcement of dissemination, or improvement of resources based on the data obtained.
- Ensuring a balanced and effective implementation of the RKH hybrid model.

2.5. System Integration and Coherence.

Although monitoring is organized across two operational levels, the analysis will be integrated, allowing for the assessment of complementarity between:

- In-person knowledge transfer.
- Continuous access to digital resources.
- Continuity of technical support.

In this way, the monitoring system ensures a comprehensive view of RKH operations within the OH FINE project, maintaining focus on implementation, operational efficiency, and activity traceability.

3. Monitoring Tools for the RKH

3.1. Physical Level – In-Person Activities.

Monitoring of each RKH's in-person activities relies on tools that enable the documentation of implementation, participation, and resource utilization.

A. Administrative and Operational Control Tools

- Operational work plan with detailed timeline.
- Implementation checklists by activity.
- Records of schedule compliance.

B. Participation Recording Tools

- Signed attendance lists.
- Beneficiary registration forms.
- Database of farmers advised.
- Record of technical consultations provided.

C. Technical Documentation Tools

- Technical activity reports.
- Minutes of meetings and advisory sessions.
- Georeferenced photographic evidence.
- Training materials delivered.

3.2. Virtual Level-Platform and Digital Services.

Monitoring of the digital environment focuses on measuring the production, availability, access, and use of resources.

Google Analytics will be used to monitor digital activities.

A. Digital Analytics Tools

- Web analytics (unique users, visits, downloads).
- Interaction metrics (session duration, clicks).
- Number of registered users.
- Tracking of online inquiries.

B. Digital Support and Assistance Tools

- Record of received inquiries.
- Ticketing or incident tracking system.
- Average response time.

C. Digital Operational Control Tools

- Automated platform activity reports.
- Indicators of update frequency.
- Access records to key resources.

3.3. Cross-cutting Tools (Integration of Both Levels)

To ensure coherence between the physical and virtual levels:

- Standardized bi-monthly report template.
- Consolidated indicator matrix.
- Regular coordination meetings.
- Monitoring dashboard.
- Centralized document management system.

4. Key Aspects to Consider in the Monitoring Plan.

4.1. Monitoring Governance.

- **Betania Legio: Monitoring Coordinator.**

Betania Legio assumes overall responsibility for the monitoring system and performs technical and operational supervision functions.

Main responsibilities:

- Design and validate the Monitoring Plan.
 - Establish common indicators and tools.
 - Consolidate information submitted by partner entities.
 - Verify data consistency, quality, and coherence.
 - Document digital evidence.
 - Identify significant deviations.
 - Propose corrective measures.
 - Prepare RKH monitoring reports.
 - Act as the liaison between the RKH.
- **CSIC, TEAG, LAMMC, WULS, and IPTP: Implementing Entities (RKH)**
Each partner entity is responsible for the operational monitoring of its own activities, at both the physical and virtual levels.

Responsibilities:

- Implement activities according to the approved plan.
- Collect implementation data using standardized tools.

- Document evidence of physical activities (reports, records, surveys, questionnaires, etc.).
- Ensure the accuracy and traceability of information.
- Submit periodic reports to Betania.
- Report incidents or deviations immediately.

Each entity will appoint a Monitoring Officer as the focal point.

- **Coordination Committee (OH- FINE Executive Board)**

Main functions:

- Review the overall progress of the RKH within the project framework.
- Validate major adjustments proposed by Betania.
- Make strategic decisions in case of significant deviations.

5. Indicators – Key Aspects to Consider in the Monitoring Plan

5.1. Physical Level Monitoring – OH FINE RKH

IMPORTANT NOTE:

Indicators will depend on the activity plan that each RKH must submit to Betania. The following is an example, which may vary depending on the activities submitted by the partners.

Examples of Activities to Monitor

- In-person workshops.
- Individual or group advisory services.
- Training courses.
- Technical sessions and demonstrations.
- Cross-visits (for experience and best practice exchange).
- Field demonstrations (practical application of organic farming techniques on pilot plots or demonstration farms).

6. Indicators – Key Aspects to Consider in the Monitoring Plan

6.1. Physical Level Monitoring – OH FINE RKH

Examples of Suggested Monitoring Indicators

Activity	Indicator	Data source	Frequency
Workshops	Number of workshops conducted vs. planned	Activity records, reports,	Every two months
Workshops	Number of participants per workshop	Attendance lists	Every workshop
Workshops	Quick Satisfaction Assessment	Brief Surveys, Questionnaire.	Every workshop
Advisory	Number of sessions conducted	Activity reports, minutes, etc.	Every two months
Advisory	Number of beneficiaries reached	Attendance records	Every two months
Advisory	Quick Satisfaction Assessment	Brief Surveys, Questionnaire	Every two months
Courses	Number of registrants vs. attendees	Attendance lists	Every course
Courses	Course completion rate (%)	Checklists, certificates	Every course
Technical sessions	Number of sessions conducted	Activity records	Every two months
Technical sessions	Number of participants	Attendance lists	Per session
Technical sessions	N° of materials generated or distributed	Record of material receipt or emails sent with the material	Per session
Field Demonstrations	Materials and Equipment Used	Internal report	Each demonstration
All	Compliance with schedule	Planned schedule vs. actual execution	Every two months

Information Collection Tools

- Signed attendance lists and records.
- Activity reports and session minutes.
- Photographic and video evidence of the demonstrations.
- Participant satisfaction forms.
- Cross-visit and demonstration reports documenting techniques, learnings, and best practices.

6.2. Virtual – OH FINE RKH

Every two months, monitoring reports will be uploaded to SACO based on data reported by Google Analytics.

Annexes

This section will include the different templates for information collection.

1. Workshop/ Training Evaluation Questionnaire
2. Advisory sessions Evaluation Questionnaire
3. Cross Visits Evaluation Questionnaire
4. Field Workshops Evaluation Questionnaire
5. Meeting with Producers Evaluation Questionnaire
6. RKHs Progress tracking (Excel)

Annex 3

Specific objectives of the awareness-raising action (Task 3.5)

Task 3.5 seeks to clearly define the specific objectives of the awareness-raising actions to be proposed within the project. These objectives will be meticulously crafted to align seamlessly with the project's overarching goals and to effectively respond to the needs and expectations of the identified target audiences.

The activity is led by CSIC within WP3, which is coordinated by ILVO. However, all partners will actively contribute to ensuring that the outcomes of the work carried out are truly useful for different national context and that potential social and cultural differences are considered.

OH-FINE aims to empower European farmers and smallholders through the definition, enhancement and transfer of competitive and efficient organic farming knowledge and alternatives that address farmer's capacities, consumer needs and evolving food market changes.

To achieve this, the project has the following specific objectives:

- SO1. To **map the current organic farming knowledge and practices, and complexity level for 5 key selected organic farming contexts** in five countries (Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Bulgaria and Spain) with different characteristics, focusing on main competitive advantages for organic producers participating in each country.
- SO2. To develop a **multidimensional framework** based on a co-creative and open innovation learning approach to organic farming knowledge development and diffusion. This will support the development and adoption of innovative practical farming models whose contribution will be assessed through a range of economic, social and environmental indicators.
- SO3. **Facilitate and promote the conversion to organic production and the capacity building of farmers the post-conversion** through training and capacity building of producers and stakeholders.
- SO4. **A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings.** The DSS ICT tool will be based on inputs from the multi-actor approach, from other official data sources, as well as inputs from SO1 and SO2, to support farmers in choosing the optimal option to organic farming practices.
- SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the **project results** and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established **communication and dissemination plan, including innovative training capsules.**

To reach these objectives, the OH-FINE project will implement **many and varied networking, knowledge-sharing and dissemination activities.**

While the main target group of the project is farmers, many other stakeholders can benefit from the networks and supportive community created in the project and the results obtained. **The target groups** for OH-FINE are as follows:

- Conventional Farmers
- Pre- and in- conversion farmers
- Post-conversion organic farmers
- Advisors
- Policymakers (regional, national, European)
- Input suppliers
- Agri-food value chain operators
- Educational/ academic community
- Scientific community
- Consumers & citizens

Thus, OH-FINE is a complex project with great potential to promote conversion to organic farming and greater economic, social and environmental sustainability in the agricultural sector.

Given this complexity and the large number and diversity of activities envisaged, it is very **important to reflect on each activity beforehand to ensure that it is properly aligned with the project's objectives and that it is appropriately designed with the target groups in mind.**

To facilitate this preliminary reflection among the project partners, an **Excel file** has been created that includes a series of guidelines for each target group. This Excel file will be completed collaboratively with contributions from the other OH- FINE partners.

The **considerations included** are as follows:

- What is OH-FINE's objective in relation to each target group?
- What specific project objectives should our activity be aligned with?
- What bottlenecks or limitations currently exist to achieve the objectives or can be found in the execution of our activities?
- What message do we want to convey to the target group and what can we consider when conveying it?
- What recommendations can be considered?
- What risks exist that could prevent the message from reaching the target group or the target group from participating in the project activities?
- How can we mitigate those risks?
- What activities can we use to convey that message?
- What materials could be useful?

The link to this Excel file will be included in the guidelines for the various activities to ensure that partners **do not lose sight of the objectives** of OH-FINE.

Annex I includes the information collected in the Excel for each target group.

ANNEX I

➤ Conventional farmers

○ Objective:

Encourage conventional farmers to consider whether organic production could be an option for them. Once they begin to value it as an option, provide them with the tools and networks to facilitate the implementation of agroecological practices, decision-making and conversion to organic farming (increase their skills).

○ Align with the project's goals

- SO3. Facilitate and promote the conversion to organic production and the capacity building of farmers the post-conversion through training and capacity building of producers and stakeholders.
- SO4. A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings.

○ Bottlenecks / Limitations

- Predisposition to believe that organic practices are less profitable.
- Lack of guidance and advice on this matter.
- Lack of networks linking organic and conventional producers and other stakeholders to exchange knowledge on organic production and agroecological practices, or lack of awareness of their existence.

○ Message

- Use figures (costs, income, profits) to show how organic production can be more profitable for them.
- The project offers farmers access to a very enriching knowledge -sharing network, activities, materials and tools to help them in their decision-making process. This will help them achieve more profitable and sustainable farms.

○ Recommendations

- Involvement of conventional farmers in the case study groups can motivate and inspire other conventional farmers in their region. A good collaboration and interaction with them to take their doubts and needs seriously is important. The experiences of colleagues as an example are very important in adoption and change.
- Conduct interactive activities in which experts can answer questions from attendees.
- Showcase the experience of organic producers in workshops and demo-activities.
- Gather their main concerns to address them in future activities.
- Promote their integration into existing networks.

○ Risks

- Information about the project's outputs and activities do not reach them.
- They do not attend activities due to lack of interest.
- They do not attend activities due to lack of availability.
- Low participation in activities (shyness or insecurity when raising questions).
- Disbelief and prejudgement.

○ Risk mitigation

- Ensure dissemination through its main channels (magazines and newspapers, cooperatives and producer organisations, digital newsletters, etc.).
- Give activities titles and approaches that may be attractive to conventional producers.
- Design activities (date/time/format) in a way that facilitate attendance.
- Have participatory methodologies in place that ensure the active participation of different types of producers and producers' personalities in activities.
- Having experts and organic producers who are also good communicators and persuasive.
- Focus during activities (and titles of the activities) on specific practices that might interest conventional farmers and not on 'organic farming' as a whole.

○ How to get the message across to them /Activities: Workshops, field demonstrations, educational material, platform, fora, network, collaborations, training, peer-to-peer learning, and dissemination of project results through the channels most used by conventional producers.

○ Materials

- Information (e.g. document) that demonstrates with figures the difference between organic and conventional production and shows other added benefits and guides them on where they can find help to switch to organic farming.
- Documents that facilitate conversion, both at the productive, bureaucratic and commercial levels.
- Videos showing how different stakeholders resolve the main doubts that producers have when considering conversion or implementing more sustainable practices.

➤ Pre- and in- conversion farmers

○ Objective:

Assist pre- and in conversion farmers in making the transition to organic farming to ensure maximum sustainability and profitability for their farms.

- **Align with the project's goals**

- SO3. Facilitate and promote the conversion to organic production and the capacity building of farmers the post-conversion through training and capacity building of producers and stakeholders.
- SO4. A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings

- **Bottlenecks / Limitations**

- Lack of guidance on this matter or lack of awareness of the existence.
- Lack of networks linking organic and conventional producers and other stakeholders to exchange knowledge on organic production and agroecological practices, or lack of awareness of their existence.
- Difficulty accessing resources tailored to their needs (considering their context and knowledge requirements), dispersion of existing resources.
- From WP2 survey results farmers perceive organic regulation / compliance as complex, fast-changing and time-consuming

- **Message:** The project offers farmers access to a very enriching knowledge -sharing network, along with targeted activities, materials and tools to help them in their decision-making process, to support the transition to organic farming and that will help them achieve more profitable and sustainable farms.

- **Recommendations**

- Encourage dynamic and interactive activities to promote knowledge sharing.
- Facilitate their inclusion in the network created.

- **Risks**

- Information about the project's outputs and activities don not reach them.
- Low participation in activities (shyness or insecurity when raising questions).
- They do not attend activities due to lack of availability.

- **Risk mitigation**

- Explore the main channels through which to convey information to them (cooperatives and other agricultural organisations, certifying bodies, AKIS, etc.).
- Have participatory methodologies in place that ensure the active participation of producers in activities.
- Design activities (date/time/format) in a way that facilitate attendance.

- **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Workshops, field demonstrations, educational material, platform, fora, network, collaborations, mentorship, training, dissemination of project results through the most suitable channels

- **Materials:** Videos and technical documents to facilitate conversion

➤ Post-conversion organic farmers

- **Objective:** Helping post-conversion organic farmers improve the profitability and sustainability of their farms (advanced organic technics, marketing, etc.)
- **Align with the project's goals**
 - SO3. Facilitate and promote the conversion to organic production and the capacity building of farmers the post-conversion through training and capacity building of producers and stakeholders.
 - SO4. A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings
- **Bottlenecks / Limitations**
 - Lack of guidance on this matter or lack of awareness of the existence.
 - Lack of/difficulty in accessing networks for sharing knowledge and experiences, or lack of awareness of their existence.
 - Difficulty accessing resources tailored to their needs (considering their context and knowledge requirements), dispersion of existing resources.
 - From WP2 survey results farmers perceive organic regulation / compliance as complex, fast-changing and time-consuming
- **Message:** The project offers them access to a very enriching knowledge - sharing network, along with targeted activities, materials and tools to help them in their decision-making process, to support post-conversion consolidation in organic farming and that will help them achieve more profitable and sustainable farms.
- **Recommendations**
 - Encourage dynamic and interactive activities to promote knowledge sharing.
 - Facilitate their inclusion in the network created.
- **Risks**
 - Information about the project's outputs and activities doesn't reach them.
 - Low participation in activities (shyness or insecurity when raising questions).
 - They do not attend activities due to lack of availability.
- **Risk mitigation**
 - Explore the main channels through which to convey the information to them (cooperatives and other agricultural organisations, certifying bodies, AKIS, organic associations, etc.).
 - Have participatory methodologies in place that ensure the active participation of producers in activities.
 - Design activities (date/time/format) in a way that facilitates attendance.
- **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Workshops, field demonstrations, educational material, platform, fora, network,

collaborations, mentorship, training, dissemination of project results through the most suitable channels.

- **Materials:** Videos and technical documents focused on post-conversion.

➤ **Advisors**

○ **Objective**

- Improve the knowledge of organic practices and marketing among advisors who currently provide advice on organic farming so that they can offer a better and more comprehensive advisory service.
- Demonstrate the advantages of organic production systems to advisers who have no experience in the field of organic production and/or are sceptical about it and improve their knowledge and advisory services.

○ **Align with the project's goals**

- SO3. Facilitate and promote the conversion to organic production and the capacity building of farmers the post-conversion through training and capacity building of producers and stakeholders.
- SO4. A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings

○ **Bottlenecks / Limitations**

- Some of the main advisors to producers do not have much time to provide advice.
- Some of the leading advisors to producers doubt that organic production can be profitable for the producers they advise.
- Lack of/difficulty in accessing networks for sharing knowledge and experiences, or lack of awareness of their existence.

○ **Message**

- The projects activities, the platform and the RKH can provide advisors with new knowledge and knowledge networks.
- The use of figures and economic data (e.g. costs, income, profits) provides solid economic evidence for sceptical advisors how organic production can be more profitable for farmers.

○ **Recommendations**

- Try to involve not only organic advisors, but also trusted advisors from conventional producers who do not have extensive and easily accessible knowledge of organic farming. If they change their mindset, they will be able to promote change among many currently conventional producers. Cross-visits and RKHs create opportunities to network / share knowledge across countries for both farmers and advisors
- Facilitate their inclusion in the network created.

- **Risks**
 - Information about the project's outputs and activities do not reach them.
 - Low participation in activities (shyness or insecurity when raising questions).
 - "Conventional" advisors do not attend activities due to lack of interest.
- **Risk mitigation**
 - Ensure dissemination through its main channels (magazines and newspapers, cooperatives and producer organisations, digital newsletters, etc.).
 - Try to engage them in a more personal way (direct phone call, meeting with several of them and an expert to show them the benefits with figures, etc.).
 - Have participatory methodologies in place that ensure the active participation of producers in activities.
- **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Workshops, field demonstrations, educational material, platform, fora, network, collaborations, training, and dissemination of project results through the most suitable channels.
- **Materials:** Videos and technical documents.
- **Policymakers (regional, national, European)**
 - **Objective**
 - Influence policymaking to support organic farming and sustainable agricultural practices.
 - Convey to them the importance of knowledge sharing in accelerating the adoption of innovations and best practices and improving the competitiveness of farms.
 - **Align with the project's goals**
 - SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan
 - **Bottlenecks / Limitations**
 - Lack of institutional culture of networking.
 - Lack of institutional awareness for agroecological practices and organic farming
 - No time or maybe not interested to attend project activities.
 - Lack of data on the impact of knowledge networks.
 - **Message**
 - Their participation in these networks is essential to improve sustainability in the agricultural sector. Convey to them the importance (with figures:

contribution to GDP, number of jobs, number of hectares, etc.) of agriculture and the potential and advantages of organic production for the region.

- Knowledge exchange networks accelerate innovation development and diffusion and improve farm competitiveness by enabling mutual learning and co-creation of solutions.

○ Recommendations

- When sending them a message to request their participation, convey the message to them.
- Regarding policy recommendations, try to meet with those who have decision-making power. Not only make and present the policy recommendations but meet with them regularly to co-create the recommendations. (often the process is more important than the recommendation itself...)
- Try to involve them as speakers or in round tables.
- Give them a better understanding of what organic production is, its economic, social and environmental potential, and the potential it may have in different regions.
- Familiarise them with the issues that limit the development of organic production, as well as possible solutions that facilitate the conversion and adoption of more sustainable and profitable practices.

○ Risks

- Lack of time.
- Lack of interest in organic production and in participating in networks.
- Scepticism/disbelieve.

○ Risk mitigation

- Notify/Contact them well in advance of events.
- Provide them information on the opportunities and advantages of organic production in the territory.
- Give them a role in the dissemination activities of the project

○ How to get the message across to them /Activities: fora, workshops and demonstrations, direct email, face-to-face meetings.

○ Materials: Policy briefs, reports.

➤ Inputs suppliers

○ Objective: Align the food chain and promote sustainable practices in the food chain.

○ Align with the project's goals

- SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan

- **Bottlenecks / Limitations:** Current availability and organic solutions are limited. For some problems encountered by producers, there are currently no effective ecological inputs.
 - **Message:** It is beneficial for inputs suppliers to participate and listen to producers to better adapt their products to demand and thus increase their business volume. This network can provide them with feedback on their products.
 - **Recommendations**
 - Collaboration with other projects focused on the supply of organic inputs could be very useful. Invite them to participate in project activities (workshops, courses related to marketing, demonstrations, etc.).
 - Provide market insights.
 - **Risks:**
 - They do not see the value in participating in the project activities.
 - Lack of time.
 - **Risk mitigation:** Organise activities where they can showcase their products and where farmers can discuss their needs with them.
 - **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Workshops, collaborations, information sessions, fora, demonstrations.
 - **Materials:** Technical documents, videos, publications.
- **Agri-food value chain operators**
- **Objective:** Align the food chain (supply-demand) and exchange information about organic farming trends, consumer preferences, and sustainable supply chain practices.
 - **Align with the project's goals**
 - SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan
 - **Bottlenecks / Limitations:** In many cases, the organic products obtained do not meet the requirements of buyers (variety, quantity of product, etc.). Volatile prices: underdeveloped markets and organic leakage (gaps in the supply chain) are highlighted by farmers in D2.5
 - **Message**
 - The consumption of organic products is on the rise. Possibility of creating stable supply networks.
 - Organic operators can make themselves known and publicise their needs (varieties, supply conditions, etc.).

- **Recommendations**
 - Collaboration with other projects focused on the value chain could be very useful.
 - Invite agri-food value chain operators to participate in project activities (workshops, courses related to marketing, demonstrations, etc.). Provide market insights.
 - Showcase successful organic case studies.
 - **Risks:**
 - They do not see the value in participating in the project activities.
 - Lack of time.
 - **Risk mitigation:** Organise networking activities where they can meet suppliers, give feedback on their product needs, difficulties they face, etc.
 - **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Workshops, collaborations, information sessions, fora, demonstrations.
 - **Materials:** Technical documents, videos, publications.
- **Educational/ academic community**
- **Objective**
 - Provide educational resources (videos, technical documents, etc.).
 - Serve as a channel for reaching young people, encouraging their participation in project activities.
 - **Align with the project's goals**
 - SO4. A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings
 - SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan
 - **Bottlenecks / Limitations**
 - Lack of organic networks to join to learn and improve and to share resources.
 - Conventional bias in curricula
 - Lack of interest in learning among some young people.
 - Some young people think they already know everything.
 - **Message**
 - The project will provide material in the local language, adapted to current information consumption patterns.
 - One possible strategy to get young people interested in the networks created by the project could be to convey to them that they can share their experiences with others, take on challenges and make practical comparisons

of certain practices, and obtain other benefits (access to new agroecological techniques, contact with other innovative producers, participation in funded projects, improved profitability and soil quality, etc.). Make it clear that there is no specific commitment to participate.

- **Recommendations**

- If there are no networks established with universities and vocational training centres, consider from the outset how the information will be communicated to them.
- Organise participatory activities aimed at gathering feedback from young people and introducing them to the success stories of organic producers.

- **Risks:** Lack of time to participate or lack of resources (e.g. transport, etc.) for them to participate.

- **Risk mitigation:** Notify the educational centre well in advance of the planned activities so that they can organise their participation in good time. If the project will facilitate aspects related to logistics that may encourage attendance.

- **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Fora, workshops, demonstrations, training courses and communication channels most used

- **Materials:** Videos, technical documents, academic publications.

➤ **Scientific community**

- **Objective:** Provision to current research data on organic farming practices and knowledge exchange, and collaboration opportunities.

- **Align with the project's goals**

- SO4. A new Decision Support System (DSS) ICT tool will be developed to maximize the exploitation and transference of the project findings
- SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan

- **Bottlenecks / Limitations**

- Lack of networks and tools to facilitate the analysis of possible synergies with other projects.
- Lack of time to conduct this analysis in depth and implement collaborations.

- **Message**

- The platform and participation in the OH-FINE network can help them publicise their activities and enrich their work.
- Collaboration between projects can generate new joint projects.

- **Recommendations:** Be active in seeking out and collaborating with other projects that may have synergies with OH-FINE.
 - **Risks:** Lack of interest in networks with other non-scientific actors due to not seeing any benefit in their participation.
 - **Risk mitigation:** Be clear about the advantages of the OH-FINE network. Projects are multi-stakeholder related and knowledge transfer is increasingly valued, so getting involved in these networks can also be important for their scientific career.
 - **How to get the message across to them /Activities:** Through networks between projects and social media (especially research centres), fora and cooperation activities organised by the European Commission and other entities.
 - **Materials:** Scientific papers, OH-FINE flyers.
- **Consumers & citizen**
- **Objective**
 - Increase consumers' knowledge about what organic production is and its advantages and implications, to promote consumption and raise society's appreciation of this type of production.
 - Inform about what European funds are used for and the advantages of working together at European level.
 - **Align with the project's goals**
 - SO5. To maximize outreach and beneficial influence of the project results and reach the target users (AKIS) through an effectively established communication and dissemination plan
 - **Bottlenecks / Limitations**
 - Limitation of consumption due to the higher prices of organic products.
 - Lack of knowledge about the advantages of organic products and how to recognise them.
 - **Message**
 - There are local consumption alternatives and seasonal products that do not necessarily mean a big increase in the cost of the shopping basket.
 - Organic production is healthy, good for the environment, taking care of the wellness of the animals and tasteful.
 - Information about organic label.
 - **Recommendations:** Participatory activities or dynamic activities that attract their attention and interest.
 - **Risks:** The proposed actions are not sufficiently appealing.

- **Risk mitigation:** Prepare activities well in advance, seeking inspiration from previous experiences or, if possible, relying on a team from your organisation that specialises in outreach activities.
- **How to get the message across to them /Activities**
 - Public campaigns, social media, community engagement activities, fairs, Science Week, European Researchers' Night.
 - Publicise initiatives of interest that promote the consumption of organic products.
- **Materials**
 - Flyers/information brochures
 - Other possible materials: Gadgets like fridge magnets, cardboard construction sets for children / masks / PVC-free stickers / colouring books / napkins, or something used at mealtimes

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